

Fast neutron response characterization of an EJ-276 plastic scintillator for use as a neutron monitor

Khai D. Ngo¹, Carlo Cazzaniga¹, Michela Paoletti^b, Davide Rigamonti^c, Maria Kastriotou¹, Christopher Frost¹, Marco Tardocchi^c, Jeff Sykora¹, Sarah Mann¹, Benjamin Lutz^d, Ralf Nolte^d

^a*UKRI-STFC, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Didcot, OX11 0QX, United Kingdom*

^b*University of Milano-Bicocca, Department of Physics, Piazza dell'Ateneo Nuovo 1, Milano, 20126, Italy*

^c*Institute for Plasma Science and Technology, CNR, Via Roberto Cozzi 53, Milano, 20125, Italy*

^d*Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Bundesallee 100, Braunschweig, 38116, Germany*

Abstract

EJ-276 is a recent development in plastic scintillators that comes with improved pulse shape discrimination over its predecessor EJ-299-33. In this work, the neutron response functions, proton light output function, and detection efficiency of EJ-276 were measured using mono-energetic neutron reference fields at the national metrology laboratory, Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, in the neutron energy range 1.5 - 19 MeV. In particular, the proton light output in the range 14 - 19 MeV is presented for the first time. The optimization of Pulse Shape Discrimination has also been investigated using an ²⁴¹Am-Be source and results are presented. Finally, we study how, using a shadow-cone method and time of flight method, we can discriminate scattered and other spurious neutrons from the mono-energetic beam. The characterized EJ-276 detector is to be used in the monitor of the neutron fields and gamma background at the new Neutron Irradiation Laboratory for Electronics facility at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

Keywords: Plastic scintillator, Pulse shape discrimination, Response function,

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*Corresponding author.

Email address: `carlo.cazzaniga@stfc.ac.uk` (Carlo Cazzaniga)
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1. Introduction

Due to the fast decay times of scintillation light and Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) capability, an EJ-276 detector is a suitable choice to perform neutron spectroscopy measurements in high count-rate environments. These properties are particularly important for monitoring and characterising beams from compact neutron sources such as those used at the new Neutron Irradiation Laboratory for Electronics (NILE) facility at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL). At NILE, high fluxes (up to $10^8 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) of 2.5 MeV and 14 MeV neutrons are produced via (d,n) reactions and are accompanied by gamma backgrounds which needs to be effectively discriminated.

Neutron-gamma discrimination is achieved by exploiting the pulse shape difference of neutron-induced and gamma-induced pulses. Liquid and single crystal organic scintillators are well-known for their PSD capabilities, however plastic scintillators have not historically exhibited this property. This changed in 2012 when the scintillation material EJ-299-33 became the first commercially available plastic scintillator with PSD [1, 2], and various extensive studies [3, 4, 5] were carried out to study the pulse shape characteristics and neutron spectroscopy capability of this material. In 2018, the EJ-276 plastic scintillator became available as a direct upgrade to EJ-299-33 [2]. A comparison study by Grodzicka-Kobylka et al. (2020) demonstrated improved PSD of EJ-276 over its predecessor however liquids like EJ-301, EJ-309, and stilbene crystals still demonstrated superior PSD [6]. Considering the disadvantages of EJ-276, degradation in time of the light output of EJ-276 was reported in [7].

Despite poorer PSD performance, plastic scintillators are more suitable for use in beamline applications. Unlike liquid scintillators, such as NE213 [8], plastic scintillators (EJ-276) are convenient to use due to their physical hardness,

27 non-toxicity, lower flammability, and ease of handling. However, PSD liquids,
28 especially EJ-309 with lower toxicity and higher flashpoint, should not be an
29 issue in a lab environment. Single crystal scintillators, like Stilbene [9], suffer
30 from other disadvantages; they are more expensive and difficult to produce and
31 can have anisotropy effects[10].

32 As such, it is expected that EJ-276 will become a popular solution for moni-
33 toring of neutron fields, and replace EJ-299-33 in field applications such as multi-
34 detector arrays [11], homeland security [12], and source identification [13].

35 In this work, the neutron response of an EJ-276 was characterised at the
36 metrology laboratory Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) in Germany.
37 One method to characterise detector response functions is using monoenergetic
38 neutrons to permit spectral unfolding of the unknown radiation fields encoun-
39 tered in applications [14]. The neutron response of the detector was studied over
40 two energy ranges: 1.6 - 5.0 MeV and 14.8 - 19.0 MeV. These energy ranges
41 are of interest because the detector will be applied to monitor the neutron field
42 and gamma background of compact neutron generators at the NILE facility. A
43 specific goal of this work was also to measure the proton Light Output Func-
44 tion (LOF) of EJ-276 scintillators. Data for this is currently limited in literature
45 when compared to other scintillators like EJ-299, EJ-309, or NE213. Only one
46 publication reporting measurements of EJ-276's LOF has been found, with the
47 neutron energies limited to a range between 170 keV and 5 MeV [7]. In this
48 work we extend the knowledge of the LOF to include the range 14.8 - 19.0 MeV.

49 **2. Experimental methods**

50 *2.1. Detector Setup and Waveform Analysis*

51 The EJ-276 is a scintillator detector produced by ELJEN TECHNOLOGY.
52 In this work, a 1 inch diameter x 1 inch height cylinder of EJ-276 was used. It
53 is coupled to a photomultiplier tube (PMT) (51 mm ET9214 PMT) with transis-
54 torised voltage divider for pulsed applications to form a detector module. Voltage
55 biases have been supplied to the detectors by a high voltage module NHQ202M
56 by ISEG (2 channels, max. 2 kV, 6 mA). The voltages were from -900 V to
57 -1100 V, depending on configuration.

58 Concerning the linearity of the PMT, both peak anode current and rate (mean
59 anode current) have to be considered. Specifications are provided by the man-
60 ufacturer with the following information. Pulsed linearity is guaranteed to be
61 $< -5\%$ deviation for peak anode currents < 100 mA. In our operations the peak
62 anode current was always < 20 mA, which is very conservative with respect to
63 the maximum. Considering rate limits, the $\Delta g/g < 1\%$ is guaranteed for mean
64 anode current < 20 μ A. In our operations the counting rate was kept < 1 kHz,
65 which corresponds to a mean anode current < 5 μ A.

66 Signals from the anode output of the PMT were fed to digitizers, CAEN-
67 DT5751 (10-bit ADC, 1 GHz sampling frequency) or CAEN-DT5730S (14-bit,
68 500 MHz), to convert the analog waveforms into digital data. Waveform data
69 were transferred to the computer's disk via USB link and saved into binary files
70 for offline analysis.

71 A Python software has been developed to perform data analysis of the scin-
72 tillator pulses. An example of an EJ-276 pulse acquired by the digitizer is illus-
73 trated in Fig. 1. This detector exhibits fast pulses with the primary scintillation

Figure 1: Example of a signal pulse acquired by the digitizer. The start of the pulse is shown as the trigger point shifted backwards by a pre-gate. The short gate and long gate of integration are indicated on the graph.

74 decay component (i.e. time of decay to $1/e$) of 13 ns. For each pulse, the code
 75 identifies the point of crossing of a threshold level. Then, it shifts backwards by
 76 a set value (called pre-gate) to identify the onset of the pulse. A baseline value
 77 is calculated by averaging of the first 16 samples of the pulse and it is subtracted
 78 from the pulse. PSD is achieved by integrating the pulse twice over the short
 79 gate and long gate, then computing a the PSD value, defined as

$$PSD = 1 - \frac{Q_s}{Q_l} \quad (1)$$

80 where Q_s and Q_l are the integrals over the short gate and long gate. A calibration

81 is used to derive the total deposited energy from Q_l .

82 2.2. Gamma Calibration

83 The integration on Q_l defines the area of the pulses. The Pulse Area (PA)
84 spectrum of the detector was calibrated using γ -ray sources of Na-22, Cs-137,
85 and Bi-207. The following energies were used for calibration: 0.511 MeV and
86 1.274 MeV for Na-22, 0.662 MeV for Cs-137, and 0.570 MeV, 1.064 MeV for
87 Bi-207 (the 1.770 MeV line of Bi-207 is not always used due to insufficient statis-
88 tics). Since full-energy-peaks are not present for the plastic EJ-276, due to its low
89 photoelectric absorption cross-section (due to low Z of the material), the Compton
90 edges of the γ -ray spectrum were used for calibration. If the energy of the
91 incident photon is E_γ (in MeV), the Compton edge has energy $2E_\gamma^2/(m_e c^2 + 2E_\gamma)$
92 (in MeV). Where m_e is the mass of the electron. The location of the Compton
93 edge has been estimated by examining the first derivative of the spectrum [15].
94 The γ -ray spectra have been smoothed (Savitzky-Golay 20-point filter) and dif-
95 ferentiated once, transforming the Compton edges into upside-down peaks in the
96 first derivative curve. Gaussian fits were applied to these peaks to give an esti-
97 mation of the PA and resolution at the Compton edge energy. A calibration plot
98 of deposited energy (E_d) by electrons against PA is shown in Fig. 2 with the
99 following fit equation

$$L = a \times (PA) + b \quad (2)$$

100 where L is the light output, and a , b are the slope and zero offset of the line,
101 respectively.

102 For the line of best fit shown in Fig. 2, $a = (1.90 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-5}$ MeV $_{ee}/(\text{PA}$
103 units), and $b = 0.053 \pm 0.007$ MeV. When this calibration is applied, electron-
104 equivalent deposited energy spectra are obtained, in units of MeV electron-

equivalent (MeV_{ee}).

Figure 2: Gamma calibration line of EJ-276 using Na-22, Cs-137, Bi-207. Deposited energy by electrons is plotted against PA. Error bars are calculated from the Gaussian fits.

105

106 2.3. Optimization of Neutron/Gamma Discrimination

107 The PSD capability of the EJ-276 has been optimized using measurements
108 performed at an Americium-Beryllium ($^{241}\text{Am-Be}$) neutron source at RAL. $^{241}\text{Am-}$
109 Be emits a broad neutron spectrum in the range 0.1-12 MeV [16]. There is also
110 an associated strong γ -ray emission, making this a good environment for PSD
111 tests. In this analysis, there were two main goals: (1) to optimize the values of
112 the short gate and long gate of the PSD algorithm and (2) to select the digitizer

113 giving the best PSD among the 10 bit - 1 Gsample and the 14 bit - 500 Msam-
 114 ple. As a note, we narrowed the selection down to these two options to have
 115 a sample rate high enough to have at least 7 samples within the Full-Width-at-
 116 Half-Maximum (FWHM), and the bit resolution as the state of the art available
 117 on the market.

Figure 3: PSD spectrum demonstrating neutron/gamma discrimination for EJ-276 at the ^{241}Am -Be source. The short gate and long gate were 60 ns and 220 ns.

118 The neutron/gamma discrimination performance is quantified by the Figure-
 119 Of-Merit (FOM) value of the PSD spectrum [17]. Given a PSD spectrum (see
 120 example in Fig.3), obtained with a histogram of all events within a thin energy
 121 range $E_{\min} < E_d < E_{\max}$, the FOM value was calculated by the following expres-

Figure 4: 2D scatterplot of PSD value versus deposited energy for EJ-276 at the $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ source, with the same time gates stated for Fig. 3.

122 sion

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{d}{\text{FWHM}_n + \text{FWHM}_\gamma} \quad (3)$$

123 where d is the separation of the centres of the peaks, and FWHM_n , FWHM_γ are
 124 the FWHM of the neutron and gamma peaks in the PSD spectrum. The centre of
 125 the peaks and FWHMs were estimated by fitting with two Gaussian peaks.

126 An example of a PSD spectrum is shown in Fig. 3, which is a projection
 127 of the 2D scatterplot of PSD value versus deposited energy (Fig. 4) onto the
 128 y-axis. Two distinct peaks, one for gamma events centred at 0.07, and another
 129 for neutron events centred at 0.16, can be observed.

Figure 5: Gate optimization for EJ-276. Left: FOM value vs long gate for short gate kept constant at 60 ns. Right: FOM value vs short gate for long gate kept constant at 220 ns. The 14 bit - 500 Msample digitizer was used.

130 The optimal time gate values were found by examining a series of PSD spectra
 131 resulting from using different combinations of time gates in the analysis.
 132 Events within the 450 to 550 keV_{ee} cut were selected, as in Ref.[6]. The dig-
 133 itizer and voltage bias were CAEN DT5730S and -900V during this procedure.
 134 Starting from an initial trial of 60 ns short gate and 220 ns long gate, the long
 135 gate was scanned while keeping the short gate constant at 60 ns. Afterwards, the
 136 short gate was scanned while keeping the long gate constant at 220 ns. Fig. 5
 137 demonstrates how the FOM value changes with the time gates. The short gate
 138 seems to affect the figure-of-merit more than the long gate does since the right

139 plot of Fig. 5 is more sharply peaked. Practically, it appears that short gate
 140 values between 50-60 ns and long gates values between 220-270 ns will result
 141 in optimal neutron/gamma discrimination. The initial guesses of 60 and 220 ns
 142 turned out to be already in the optimal range and were therefore applied to all
 143 subsequent analyses. Another measurement with the ^{241}Am -Be source was car-
 144 ried out with the CAEN DT5751 replacing the DT5730S model. The FOM value
 145 was calculated to be 0.672 ± 0.005 for the 10 bit - 1Gsample DT5751 and 0.877
 146 ± 0.005 for the 14 bit - 500 Msample DT5730S. Therefore, the CAEN DT5730S
 147 digitizer was used for all subsequent measurements.

148 3. Measurements with mono-energetic neutrons

149 3.1. Neutron beams at PIAF

Reaction	Target	E_n (MeV)	ΔE_n (keV)
T(p,n) ^3He	Ti(T) 2 mg/cm 2	<u>2.5</u>	<u>103</u>
T(p,n) ^3He	Ti(T) 2 mg/cm 2	2.65	91
D(d,n) ^3He	D $_2$ 850 hPa	5.0	124
T(d,n) ^4He	Ti(T) 1 mg/cm 2	<u>14.8</u>	<u>435</u>
T(d,n) ^4He	Ti(T) 1 mg/cm 2	16	409
T(d,n) ^4He	Ti(T) 2 mg/cm 2	19.0	250

Table 1: Reactions and targets used at PTB to achieve the desired reference field of mean energy E_n and beam width ΔE_n at 0° with respect to the ion beam direction. In bold: time-of-flight data taken. Underlined: shadow cone spectrum taken.

150 At the PTB Ion Accelerator Facility (PIAF), neutron reference fields are pro-
 151 duced by accelerating a beam of protons or deuterons at a solid or gas target [18].

2.65 MeV		5.0 MeV		19.0 MeV	
α (deg)	E_n (MeV)	α (deg)	E_n (MeV)	α (deg)	E_n (MeV)
0	2.65	<u>0</u>	<u>5.0</u>	0	19.0
40	2.19	55	4.0	28	18.48
49	2.00	85	3.0	40	17.99
58	1.80			50	17.48
67	1.60			58	17.03
				67	16.48
				75	15.98
				83	15.47

Table 2: Angle α in degrees and mean energy E_n in MeV for three standard neutron fields when E_n at 0 deg is 2.65 MeV, 5.0 MeV, and 19.0 MeV. In bold: time-of-flight data taken. Underlined: shadow cone spectrum taken.

152 The monoenergetic neutron fields were produced according to the general rec-
153 ommendations of the ISO standards [19, 20, 21]. The ion beam was accelerated
154 by a Tandatron accelerator producing a pulsed beam with a repetition frequency
155 of 2.5 MHz and pulse duration of about 2 ns. Table 1 summarises the main reac-
156 tions used at PTB in this study along with the neutron energy E_n and beam width
157 ΔE_n of the mono-energetic fields at 0° with respect to the ion beam direction.
158 Energies lower than the listed energies in Table 1 were reached by changing the
159 detector's viewing angle with respect to the ion beam direction. The angles used
160 and the neutron energy at that position are summarised in Table 2.

161 The EJ-276 detector was placed at a fixed distance of 150.05 ± 0.20 cm away
162 from the neutron production target (distance is between the detector front surface

163 and target surface), on one of the swivel arms in the low scatter experimental hall
164 (see Fig. 6a). The position of the detector was aligned by laser such that neutrons
165 were impinging perpendicular to the surface and along the axis of the cylindrical
166 scintillator. The temperature in the measurement hall during the measurements
167 was (21.5 ± 1.0) C.

168 For metrology measurements, the fluence of direct neutrons at the reference
169 position was determined using a De Pangher long counter. Details of the mea-
170 surement and analysis procedures are described in [22]. The neutron energy dis-
171 tribution at the different measurement locations is calculated using the dedicated
172 Monte Carlo code TARGET [23]. This code simulates the specific geometry of
173 the PTB target assembly and takes into account the interactions with the target
174 materials of the primary ions as well as the generated neutrons.

Figure 6: Detector setup at PTB for (a) total field measurement and (b) background measurement only with shadow cone.

175 3.2. Direct Neutron Selection

176 Two different methods have been used in this study to remove the background
177 and select only mono-energetic direct neutrons: a shadow-cone setup, and Time

(a)

Figure 7: Example of a scatter-plot of PSD values versus Light Output for the case of $E_n = 16$ MeV. Neutrons can be seen clustered above the red discrimination line, γ -rays are clustered below the discrimination line.

178 of Flight (ToF) discrimination. This is done on top of the PSD discrimination
 179 (see example in Fig.7).

180 The shadow cone setup [24, 25, 26] consist in placing a shielding element
 181 of conical form of 200 mm of steel (small diameter side orientated to the tar-
 182 get) and 300 mm of polyethylene (large diameter side orientated to the detector)
 183 between the detector and the target (see picture in Fig. 6b). When the cone is
 184 in place, direct neutrons are stopped, so that only background neutrons from the
 185 hall are recorded. The measurement is repeated with and without the shadow-

186 cone, so that background neutrons can be subtracted from the measurement. The
187 shadow-cone method was not available for all runs because it is considerably
188 time-consuming and a choice was made to use it only for selected energy val-
189 ues. In Tables 1 and 2, runs that had the shadow cone technique available are
190 underlined.

Figure 8: The total, direct, and back-scattered neutron response spectra of EJ-276 for 2.5 MeV neutrons.

191 Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the neutron responses to 2.5 MeV and 14.8 MeV
192 neutrons for EJ-276. For these measurements the shadow-cone technique was
193 available. The back-scattered neutron spectra obtained from shadow cone mea-
194 surements, shown on the same figure, were subtracted from the total neutron

Figure 9: The total, direct, and back-scattered neutron response spectra of EJ-276 for 14.8 MeV neutrons.

195 spectra, and γ -rays are rejected by PSD, to obtain the direct neutron response.
 196 The combined spectra of direct and back-scattered neutron responses demon-
 197 strate that background corrections are small: back-scattered neutrons only ac-
 198 count for less than 2% of the total counts. This is thanks to the low scattering
 199 hall available at PTB. Response functions for 2.5 MeV and 14.8 MeV neutrons
 200 were collected with the best statistics, as they are the most interesting cases for
 201 fusion neutron generators.

202 When performing Time of Flight (ToF) measurements [27, 28, 29], "start sig-
 203 nals" from an accelerator, operated in pulsed mode, are recorded by the digitizer

Figure 10: Example of a Time-of-flight spectrum of a neutron measurement for EJ-276 for the case of $E_n = 16$ MeV.

204 on a second channel in coincidence with the detector pulse. The time difference
 205 Δt between "start signal" and pulse is then measured. The timing of a signal
 206 crossing the threshold is calculated by applying interpolation in order to achieve
 207 better time resolution than the digitizer sampling rate. As the time shift of the
 208 signals travelling through the cables is an unknown, a constant shift ϕ needs to
 209 be applied to calibrate the ToF, $ToF = \Delta t + \phi$. This is done by imposing the
 210 speed of light for the γ -ray peak, which is the first peak in the ToF spectrum. An
 211 example of a resulting ToF spectrum is shown in Fig. 10 for the measurement
 212 with 16 MeV neutrons. Here one can see the γ -ray peak, followed by the direct

Figure 11: EJ-276's response function to 16 MeV neutrons after background correction using PSD and time-of-flight data and shadow cone measurement.

213 neutrons of the $T(d,n)^4\text{He}$ reaction, followed by the neutrons of the parasitic re-
 214 action $D(d,n)^3\text{He}$ that can be discarded. The latter component results from the
 215 deuterium impurity present in the tritium targets. A continuous background due
 216 to scattered neutrons does not have any ToF features. In conclusion, for this ex-
 217 ample of 16 MeV neutrons, only events lying above the red curve in Fig. 7 (PSD
 218 discrimination) and within the 27 ns peak in Fig. 10 (TOF discrimination) are
 219 considered to be induced by direct neutrons. When repeating the measurements
 220 using also the shadow-cone method, after PSD and ToF discrimination, we can
 221 observe that shadow-cone counts are very suppressed. Fig.11 shows the exam-

222 ple at 16 MeV. Total counts are presented, as well as the counts to be subtracted
223 thanks to PSD and ToF discrimination, and shadow-cone counts. After subtract-
224 ing these contributions we are left with the counts due to direct neutrons only.
225 Runs where ToF data are available are marked in bold in Tables 1-2. If a mea-
226 surement had both ToF and shadow-cone technique available, it is both in bold
227 and underlined.

228 It is to be noted that the shadow-cone and the ToF method are not exactly
229 equivalent. The shadow cone method cannot subtract low-energy neutrons re-
230 sulting from target scattering. The TOF method has difficulty subtracting neutron
231 scattering at very small angles in the air between the detector and the target.

232 **4. Results**

233 *4.1. Neutron Response Functions*

234 All response functions in the lower energy range 1.6 MeV to 5 MeV are
235 presented in Fig. 12 and response functions in the higher energy range 14.8
236 MeV to 19 MeV are presented in Fig. 13. Data were sorted into 50-keV_{ee}-
237 wide bins for responses in the high energy region, while 4-keV_{ee}-wide bins were
238 used for responses in the low energy region. The response function are, in first
239 approximation, a box shape, as expected from the elastic recoil of fast neutrons
240 on protons. In fact, protons can receive any energy from zero to the maximum
241 neutron energy, depending on the angle of recoil [30]. The box-shape function
242 is then distorted by the light output non-linearity and by second order events like
243 multiple scattering [31].

244 Interestingly, for the high energies (Fig. 13) there is a step at low Light
245 Output (about < 1 MeV_{ee} mark). This is due to reactions of neutrons on Car-
246 bon that are "open" at these energies: $^{12}\text{C}(n, \alpha)^9\text{Be}$ with threshold 6.19 MeV,

Figure 12: EJ-276's direct neutron response functions in the energy region of 1.6 - 5.0 MeV.

247 $^{12}\text{C}(n, n3\alpha)$ with threshold 8.8 MeV, $^{12}\text{C}(n, p)^{12}\text{Be}$ with threshold 13.7 MeV and
 248 $^{12}\text{C}(n, d)^{11}\text{Be}$ with threshold 14.9 MeV. These components of the response func-
 249 tions have been studied in details for the case of a NE213 using GEANT4 sim-
 250 ulations by Garcia et al. [32]. For this, one needs also to consider that the light
 251 output of α is less than the light output of protons [33]. Finally, elastic recoil on
 252 Carbon is also present, but C nuclei can only receive up to 28% of the kinetic
 253 energy of the incident neutron and would produce much less scintillation light
 254 compared to protons and α -particles [33].

255 All spectra presented in this section are normalised to the total number of
 256 neutrons arriving at the detector. The total number of neutrons was calculated by

Figure 13: EJ-276's direct neutron response functions in the energy region of 14.8 - 19 MeV.

257 multiplying the measured neutron fluence value, calibrated by PTB's detectors,
 258 with the front surface area (i.e. the cross section area) of the scintillator. The
 259 detector efficiency can be calculated by integrating the response functions from
 260 a threshold to the end of the spectrum. Fig. 14 shows the detection efficiency of
 261 EJ-276. Here two different detection thresholds are applied for the lower energy
 262 and higher energy range, 300 keV_{ee} and 2 MeV_{ee} , respectively. The lower energy
 263 threshold of 300 keV_{ee} has been selected to cut the low energy region where gam-
 264 mas and neutrons overlap. The upper 2 MeV_{ee} threshold has been selected for the
 265 high energies to also cut the contribution of the reactions on carbon. The circled
 266 points marked with a letter M are runs that had absolute fluence measurements

267 provided by PTB following metrology standards. For the other points the total
268 fluence of neutrons had to be calculated without following metrology standards,
269 estimating the ratio of neutrons emitted at a certain angle from simulations, and
270 normalising to the accelerator current. There are two sources of uncertainties in
271 the detection efficiency: the counting statistics of the neutron response spectrum
272 and the uncertainty in the absolute neutron fluence measurement. The percent-
273 age uncertainties of these sources in this case add in quadrature. Since there were
274 more than 100 000 neutron events in every run, which by Poisson statistics im-
275 plies a percentage uncertainty of less than 0.3%, the uncertainty in the neutron
276 fluence is more dominant, which varies between 2-4% in comparison. Hence,
277 uncertainties in the detection efficiency were propagated from the uncertainty in
278 the neutron fluence measurement, and the error bars in Fig. 14 represent one
279 sigma confidence interval. The fact that all the results of Fig.14 fall on the same
280 curve, regardless if ToF was applied or not, means that the PSD cut is adequate
281 to fully suppress the gamma contribution, which would already be low due to the
282 low scattering hall of PTB.

283 *4.2. Light Output Function*

284 The position of the maximum recoil proton energy edge was evaluated us-
285 ing a technique described by Kornilov et al. [34]. The response spectra were
286 smoothed and differentiated once, and a Gaussian fit was applied to the differ-
287 entiated edge to give an estimate of the light output of the recoiled proton. This
288 allowed the construction of the recoil proton Light Output Function for EJ-276,
289 presented in Fig. 15. Uncertainties in the proton light output were propagated
290 from uncertainties in the pulse area - light output calibration and from the finite
291 energy bin width of the neutron response spectra. The error bars are smaller

Figure 14: EJ-276's detection efficiency from 1.6 - 5.0 MeV for a detection threshold of 300 keV_{ee}, and from 14.8 - 19.0 MeV for an energy threshold of 2 MeV_{ee}. The circled points with a letter M next to them had absolute neutron fluence measurements.

292 than the data points to be seen in Fig. 15. Light output data for EJ-299-33 from
 293 Lawrence et al. [35] and for EJ-276 from Laplace et al. [7] are plotted on the
 294 same graph for comparison. The result of Fig. 15 shows that both EJ-276 and
 295 its predecessor have very similar light output in the range of $1.60 < E_p < 3.0$
 296 MeV, with deviations of less than 1%, as noted by Ryabeva et al. [36]. Up to
 297 $E_p < 5$ MeV, the results obtained in this paper are below Lawrence et al.'s data
 298 for EJ-299-33 by approximately 10%, while Laplace et al.'s data for EJ-276 are
 299 always 10-30% greater than this work's data. It has to be noted that Laplace et

Figure 15: EJ-276’s scintillation light output relation for recoil proton energy. The data was fitted using the empirical model given in Eq. (4). The error bars are smaller than the data points.

300 al. used a longer integration length (350 ns). We studied the contribution of this
 301 fact using the data acquired at PTB and we found a discrepancy of always less
 302 than 4%. This is a bias that the reader should certainly take into account if trying
 303 to replicate these measurements. This small bias is introduced by some residual
 304 light that is not included in the integration, as well as potential fluctuation in
 305 the baseline level. One of the advantages of a shorter integration length is the
 306 application in higher counting rate environments, limiting data throughput and
 307 computing times, and reducing the probability of pile-up. The results presented
 308 in this work extend the curve of EJ276 to the energy range $14 \text{ MeV} < E_p < 20$

309 MeV that is data that was missing in literature. The light output data of EJ-276
310 was fitted using the following empirical model [35]

$$L = aE_p - b(1 - e^{-cE_p}) \quad (4)$$

311 where L is the light output, E_p is the energy of the recoil proton, and a , b , c are
312 the function fit parameters. These parameters were calculated to be: $a = 0.73$
313 ± 0.02 , $b = 3.5 \pm 0.3$, and $c = 0.20 \pm 0.02$, respectively. matrix is provided in
314 Tab.A.2. A study by Norsworthy et al. [37] suggests that different fit functions
315 can also be used, and be more optimal in certain cases. The study by Norsworthy
316 [37] also shows that the extrapolations of the different models to lower energies
317 < 1 MeV are diverging (see Fig.2 of [37]). The good fit of this empirical model
318 with data suggests that this is more than adequate for application in the 1-20 MeV
319 energy range, which is enough for our application needs of characterisation of
320 the NILE facility. The readers could feel confident about using these data within
321 this energy range, but due to the nonphysical nature of the model, extrapolations
322 to lower energies are not to be trusted.

323 5. Outlook

324 The fully characterised EJ-276 detector will be applied in monitoring the
325 radiation fields of the new NILE facility at RAL. Here, neutron production is
326 achieved by Deuterium-Deuterium (DD) and Deuterium-Tritium (DT) fusion in
327 compact neutron generators. In these sources, deuterium gas at low pressure is
328 ionised by microwaves and accelerated by a voltage bias (100-120 kV) towards
329 a deuterium-implanted (or tritium-implanted) metal target. The neutron energy
330 is 2.5 MeV for DD and 14 MeV for DT, although there are several effects to be
331 studied, that is the energy angular variation [38], the width of the neutron peak,

332 and the contribution of scattered neutrons. It is of practical interest to use the
333 EJ-276 detector, and others, to study the neutron fields at different irradiation
334 positions. The main application of NILE will be testing of microelectronics for
335 single event effects, requiring a good knowledge of fluences delivered to the
336 devices under tests by the users.

Figure 16: Pulse height spectra of EJ-276 at NILE DT source compared to at PTB 14.8 MeV neutron.

337 A preliminary measurement of the DT source using the EJ-276 detector is
338 shown in Fig. 16. The pulse height spectrum was normalised using the detec-
339 tion efficiency measured at PTB for 14.8 MeV neutrons (detection threshold 2
340 MeV_{ee}). In the figure the spectrum is compared with the 14.8 MeV measurement

341 at PTB. The following effects can already be noticed and will be studied in future
342 work: i) the recoil proton edge for the NILE measurement is centred to the left of
343 the PTB one, as expected the mean energy is < 14.8 MeV. ii) The recoil proton
344 edge is less sharp, as the energy spread ΔE of the peak should be larger at NILE
345 then at PTB. iii) the low energy part of the spectrum is higher, as in fact at NILE
346 there is no low scatter hall, so the scattered neutron component is expected to
347 be considerably higher than at PTB. Spectrum unfolding [39, 40, 41] or forward
348 fitting [42] should be studied as future analysis for NILE.

349 **6. Conclusions**

350 An experimental characterization of the response of EJ-276 scintillator to
351 mono-energetic fast neutrons has been presented in this paper. The detector's
352 γ -ray discrimination capabilities have been tested, and methods to discriminate
353 direct mono-energetic neutrons from other sources of background have been im-
354 plemented. Experimental response functions in the range 1.5 MeV to 20 MeV
355 are presented together with absolute detection efficiency that, for some of the
356 energies, is calibrated to metrology standards. Finally, the results presented here
357 extend the measured energy range up to 20 MeV and determine values which fit
358 well with a prior empirical light output model. Due to this characterization work,
359 the EJ-276 detector will be used to study the radiation field at a new facility with
360 compact neutron generators at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

361 **Appendix A. Experimental Data**

362 See Table A.1 for detection efficiency and proton light output data of EJ-276.

363

Recoil Proton Energy (MeV)	Light Output (MeV _{ee})	Detection Efficiency	
		300 keV _{ee}	2 MeV _{ee}
1.59	0.239 ± 0.051	0.0032 ± 0.0001	
1.79	0.289 ± 0.051	0.0159 ± 0.0004	
1.99	0.338 ± 0.051	0.0412 ± 0.0010	
2.19	0.393 ± 0.051	0.0630 ± 0.0015	
2.50	0.489 ± 0.051	0.0909 ± 0.0021	
2.65	0.528 ± 0.051	0.1005 ± 0.0024	
3.00	0.679 ± 0.051	0.1116 ± 0.0022	
4.00	1.01 ± 0.05	0.1249 ± 0.0025	
5.00	1.47 ± 0.05	0.1196 ± 0.0024	
14.8	7.53 ± 0.09		0.0464 ± 0.0010
15.5	7.87 ± 0.10		0.0401 ± 0.0014
16.0	8.27 ± 0.10		0.0416 ± 0.0015
16.5	8.66 ± 0.10		0.0398 ± 0.0014
17.0	9.07 ± 0.11		0.0434 ± 0.0015
17.5	9.51 ± 0.11		0.0429 ± 0.0015
18.0	9.93 ± 0.12		0.0449 ± 0.0016
18.5	10.3 ± 0.1		0.0419 ± 0.0015
19.0	10.7 ± 0.1		0.0392 ± 0.0014

Table A.1: Proton light output and detection efficiency data (at 300 keV_{ee} and 2 MeV_{ee} thresholds) with their experimental uncertainties for EJ-276.

	A	B	C
A	3.57128E-4	0.00643	-3.0075E-4
B	0.00643	0.11926	-0.00567
C	-3.0075E-4	-0.00567	2.71886E-4

Table A.2: Covariance Matrix for the fit parameters of eq.4

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